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Reaping pest-free ber

Ber is an important fruit crop for arid and semi-arid region and an extremely drought hardy and native fruit of India. At present, 130 species of insect-pests have been recorded in India but only few species have attained the pest status and cause substantial economic damage to ber. Out of these, 3 insects species, viz. fruit fly, *Carpomyia vesuviana*, fruit borer, *Meridarchis scyroides* and stone weevil, *Aubeus himalayanus* were recorded as major pests. Whereas two insects species, viz. butter fly, *Tarucus theophrastus* and thrips, *Scirtothrips dorsalis* were recorded as moderate pests. As many as 7 insect species, viz. *Mylocerus dentifer*, *M. blandus*, *Amblyrrhinus poricollis*, *Synclera univocolis*, *Larvacarus transitans*, *Indarbela* sp. and *Odontotermes* sp. were recorded as minor pests. For managing them, some simple management (IPM) tactics that keep away the insect-pests and alleviate the chemical methods are recommended.

BER (*Ziziphus mauritiana*) is also known as desert apple, jujube, Chinese apple, Ber (Hindi), Indian plum and Permseret (Anguilla) is a tropical fruit tree species, belonging to the family Rhamnaceae. The crop is gaining popularity among the growers because it thrives well under adverse climatic condition and gives good return. Ber has been found as an immune stimulant, anti-biotic, anti-nephritic, antiulcer, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant. The fruits are quit nutritious, contains higher quantity of vitamin C, second only to aonla and guava and much higher than citrus and apple.

MANAGEMENT OF INSECT PESTS

Fruit Fly

Fruit fly (*C. vesuviana*) is most destructive pest of ber in India. It is a monopahagous pest, infests only on *Zizyphus* species and contributes low yield

and poor quality fruits. The pest causes the yield loss up to 80% under severe infestation. The female fly lays their eggs singly on young developing fruits after 2-5 days after emergence. They lay their eggs inside the epidermis and young maggots feed on fleshy and juicy pulp of fruits.

Upon hatching, the maggot starts to feed on the pulp and make galleries with accumulated excreta and resulted to fruit rot. The larva burrow the flesh around the center, leaving excreta that gives fruits a bitter taste. Adult fly also damaged the fruits by making ovi-punctures. The female preferred to oviposit at central distal part fruit and the oviposition retard the growth of surrounding tissues causing depression in the fruits and deformity is most apparent in young fruits with oviposition holes. The infestation occurs during November to April and activity was very high at the time of fruit maturity in Northern India. In Central India, the

Healthy plant of ber

Fruit fly infected ber fruits

Adult fruit fly

fruit fly attack starts around mid-October and increased abruptly during mid-November and continues till December. The pupa hibernates in the soil during April to August shows unusual activity of fly during off season fruits of ber.

Integrated approaches should be better control with low cost and environmentally safe. Clean cultivation surrounding the orchard through destruction of pruned parts of plant. Deep summer ploughing with racking up of soil to expose the residual pupa and destroy the over wintering pupae. Use of resistance varieties like Tikadi, Katha and Illaichi for fruit fly control. The biological agents like *Biostres vandenboschi*, *Bracon fletcheri*, *Opius carpomyia*, *Fopius carpomyia* and *Omphalia* sp. for control of fruit fly. The extract of azadiractin 1% and *Ocimum sanctum* 1% were effective to control the fruit fly. Bait spray combining molasses or jaggery 10 g/l and one of the insecticides, malathion 50 EC 2 ml/l or dimethoate 30 EC 2ml/l of two rounds at fortnight interval before ripening of the fruits.

Stone Weevil

For first time, stone weevil (*A. himalayanus*) was recorded as a new pest of ber from Andhra Pradesh,

Stone weevil damage

Stone weevil egg laying site

later, from Rahuri, Maharashtra and Jobner, Rajasthan and recently in Bikaner district of Rajasthan in 2010. Grubs directly damage the fruits by tunneling inside seeds and adult weevil also blemishes mature fruit by ovi-punctures. The adult female weevil lays their eggs mostly on the styler end; rarely on the distal end of fruits and egg laid punctures covered with brown encrustation. Upon hatching, the grubs enter into seed by puncturing endocarp at immature stage and starts feeding on soft seed coat. Later it enters into endosperm moving downward. After entering the seed, it starts feeding on inner content of the seed, and pupates within the seed by making hallow galleries.

The weevil completes its life within a single fruit. The developing soft seed was completely eaten away by the pest. At the time of fruit maturity, in the hollowed area, infested fruits had a grub, a pupa or an adult. The infestation occurs in all the fruit stages; however, it is prevalent in pea to pebble size fruits. The activity of adult weevil starts from month of September and adults starts the egg laying from blooming stage onwards and severe damage could be observed during October month. The incidence could be noticed still at the end of fruiting upto February month.

Adult stone weevil

Collection and destruction of adult weevil immediately after detection can also reduce the population. Infested fruits should be collected and burned to break the generation cycle. Deep summer ploughing to expose the residual adult in hot

Fruit borer damage

Adult (left) and larvae (right) of fruit borer

summer. The varieties of ber like Kali, Katha, Illaichi and Tikadi were found resistant to stone weevil. NSKE 5% and azadirachtin 2000 ppm and 1000 ppm were found best to minimizing the weevil incidence. Application of spinosad 2.5 SC and indoxacarb 14.5 EC or dimethoate 30 EC just before the fruit setting and repeat the sprays at three weeks interval was found effective and showed significant reduction in weevil incidence.

Fruit Borer

The fruit borer (*M. scyroides*) is a serious pest in Southern states like Gujarat, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka. The pest causes up to 70% yield loss under severe infestation. The moths lay eggs on fruits at pea stage and upon hatching the newly emerged caterpillars bore into fruits and feed on the pulp near seed and accumulate fecal. The first and second instar larvae feeds on the fruit superficially but third to fifth instar larvae feeds internally and damages the pulp around the seed. At initial stages of fruit development, the full grown larvae found to feed on soft immature seed. The infestation starts during month of November and the peak incidence occurs during end of December. The damage intensity found to be positively correlated with the temperature and negatively correlated with the relative humidity and wind speed.

The adult female lays an average of 13 eggs and incubation period was found to be 4-5 days. The larval and pupal stages completed in 14-18 and 8-9 days, respectively. The life cycle completes within 26-32 days. Longevity of adult male and female were observed 3-4 and 4-5 days, respectively.

Removal of wild ber trees around the ber orchard. Rack the soil under the tree or near the trees to destroy the maggots and residual pupae present in the soil. Growing of resistant cultivars like Safeda, Illaichi and Tikadi to found less incidence of fruit borer. Methanol extracts of *Annona reticulata*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Ocimum sanctum* at 1% concentration recorded 60-70% mortality after 48 h after spray. Sprays of dimethoate 30 EC + jaggery solution (1.0%) at marble stage and one spray at maturation stage resulted in minimum infestation and found to be more economical. Control schedule comprises of malathion at 2 ml/liter of water first spray at marble stage, second spray at 15 days later and third spray at fruit ripening stage by alternate use of insecticides would be effective against the fruit borer.

Ber Butterfly

The blue butterfly (*T. theophrastus*) is an important defoliator pest of ber. The infestation occurs on new sprouts and distributed throughout the ber growing region of Karnataka, Rajasthan, Haryana and Punjab. Pest causes the leaf damage up to 25-40% during sprouting of new shoots. The larvae also damage the flower buds and tender shoots. Larvae feeds on newly sprouting tender shoots, leaves and flower buds. Infested leaf gives whitish look due to chlorophyll feeding and leaves remains with long streaks.

The infestation starts from June and peak incidence occurs during third week of October with a peak population in the first week of August. The population showed positive correlation with maximum and minimum temperatures and negative correlation with relative humidity and rainfall. The metallic blue colour butterfly, having the wing tail in the posterior end of the hind wing. The larvae

Ber butterfly damage

Adult (left) and larvae (right) of ber butterfly

Bark eating caterpillar damage

are small flat, green in colour with sparse hairs on their body. Most of the time larvae are associated with the ant due their sugary secretion from anus.

Spray of dimethoate, @ 2 ml/litre of water would be most effective against 3rd to 6th instar larvae. Quinalphos (0.05%) and triazophos (0.1%) also would effectively reduce the larval population and leaves damage.

in petrol or kerosene also can place in the holes and sealed with mud.

of one litre of kerosene with 100g of soap in 9 litre of water to the holes has been found to be effective against caterpillar. Inject the holes with quinalphos at 0.01% or fenvalerate at 0.05% and alternate spray of quinalphos at 2ml per litre of water found to be effective in controlling the caterpillar damage. Cotton swab soaked

Termite

Termite (*O. obesus*) causes damage to the seedlings and budded plants and about 49 per cent of ber tree were found to be infested with termite. The activity is mainly on the bark of main trunk.

Frequent irrigation reduces the infestation of termite. Drenching with clothianidin 50 WDG at concentration of 1ml/ litre of water reduce the infestation of termites.

Adults of different weevils

Weevil damage

Bark-eating Caterpillar

The incidence of bark-eating caterpillar *Indarbela tetraonis*, *Indarbela quadrinotata* pest is found throughout the ber growing region of India especially old orchards and trees which are in poor maintenance. The bark eating caterpillar damages can be easily detected by presence of frassy webs at forks or angle. The moth lays their eggs on bark of the branches, upon hatching they settle at forks or angles of braches and feeds on bark during night, remaining concealed during daytime in tunnel made at junction of branches. Feeding on bark hardly affects plants, it is tunnel made by larva for its shelter, which inflicts the actual loss. The junction point is rendered weak due to tunnel. During bearing period when fruits develop, pressure at forks is greatly increased due to weight of fruits, resulting in cleavage of branch at fork or angle and its drying. The attack of caterpillars starts June onwards and fresh web galleris observed till October month.

Periodical cleaning of orchard and removal of webs/frassy galleries around affected portion at the time of pruning and destruction of caterpillar using iron spike in hole. The cultivars Rothak Gola, Laddu Glory, Chuhhara and Desi Alwar are found tolerant to bark eating caterpillar. Painting of bark with dimethoate 0.05% was effective control. Application

Ber Weevil

Ber weevil (*M. dentifer*, *M. blandus* and *Amblyrrhinus poricollis*) are minor pest of ber. It is a polyphagous pest occurring on ber. The adult beetles feed on leaves of ber. Damage can range from notching on the leaf margins to much more extensive feeding along the leaf veins.

Adults lay their eggs in the soil lay their eggs in the soil. Larvae are small, creamy white, and legless. They are root feeders. Adults can cause severe feeding damage to the foliage. *M. dentifer* body is blackish in color with brownish spots. *M. blandus* body is dark brown in color. *A. poricollis* body is light brown in color with whitish strips on body.

Adult weevils can be removed from plants by vigorously shaking a branch over an open, inverted umbrella. The collected weevils can then be dumped into a container of soapy water. Apply Neem cake @ 500 kg/ha at the time of last ploughing. Spray of insecticide dimethoate or malathion 2 ml per litre of water during sever incidence of weevil.

For further interaction, please write to
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